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Research Article

EMERGING ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE PATTERN OF E. COLI UTI: A SINGLE CENTER STUDY

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Abstract:

***Objective:** To determine the frequency and patient demographics of multidrug resistant (MDR) urinary tract isolates of Escherichia Coli (E. coli) in a tertiary care hospital.*

***Study Design:** Retrospective study*

***Setting:** The study was conducted in departments of Medicine and Obstetrics & Gynecology, Madinah Teaching Hospital / University Medical and Dental College, and General Hospital, Faisalabad.*

***Duration of Study:** Study was conducted from May 2016 to Sep 2018.*

***Results:** In this retrospective study, 187 cases of UTI with a positive culture showing E. coli were identified from 2015 to 2018. Among all the cases of E. coli UTI, frequency of MDR was 66.8% (n=125) and rest 33.2% (n= 62) cases were not MDR UTI. Among the MDR E.coli UTI cases, 99% of the cases were resistant to one or more antimicrobials of the aminoglycoside family (which was statistically significant, p = 0.000).*

***Keywords:** UTI, MDR, Multi-drug resistance, E. coli, Gram negative, Urinary infection, Cystitis, Urine culture*

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INTRODUCTION:

Infections of the renal tract including kidneys, ureter and bladder affect humans of a age groups. Around one fourth of all the patients presenting with some sort of infection in the hospitals have urinary tract infection (UTI). [1] Bacteriuria with or without any complaints regarding renal system or with vague symptoms can still be labeled as UTI. The condition, Bacteriuria can be defined as the presence of more than 10^5 colony forming units (CFU) in one ml urine sample. [2]

A study reported that about a million patients present with UTI symptoms visit daily in emergency globally; with a large number of hospital admissions as well. These symptoms include burning sensation with passage of urine, frequent urge to pass urine, low abdominal pain or pain in the back, sometimes urine become cloudy or darker than normal and even smelly along with generalized malaise with tiredness. [3,4]

Normal flora apart from the GI tract can also reside in the urethra. These include *S. epidermidis*, *S. faecalis*, and *Corynebacterium*. With urinary tract infection microbes climb up the renal tract from the urethra to bladder and start to grow. Most of these microbes are fecal borne. More than three fourth of these infections are caused by a fecal borne microbes names *E.coli*. The earlier we get rid of this infection from the urinary tract the lesser the morbidity can be and complications can be avoided. [5]

Multiple antibiotics are used to treat *E. coli* UTI cases. These include nitrofurantoin or trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole for uncomplicated cases and quinolones, ceftriaxone, aminoglycosides, and carbapenems for infections ureter and kidneys or multiple parts of tract. With the miss-use of antibiotics, there is rise in the multidrug-resistant (MDR) cases of Enterobacteriaceae UTI. Every population has its own pattern of antibiotic resistance. [6]

A local study conducted in Multan, reported MDR *E. coli* isolates resistant pattern of 80% (IMI), 72% (Cip), 68% (Aug), 60% (Cfm), and 52% (CN), respectively, while these microbes were sensitive to TZP (70%), AK (62%), and F (60%).

We collected data and reported the demographic variables and prevalence of MDR *E. coli* UTI cases of our local population, Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan. In this second phase, antimicrobial sensitivity pattern was analyzed for these cases. Primary objective of this study was to determine the emerging antibiotic

resistance pattern of MDR UTI cases caused by *E.Coli* at Madinah Teaching Hospital and General Hospital, Faisalabad.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This retrospective study included 187 patients meeting the operational definition of multi-drug resistance cases of urinary tract infections caused by *E. coli*. The objective of this study was to determine the antibiotic resistance pattern of these drug resistant cases of *E. coli* UTI. This was conducted in the department of Medicine, Madinah Teaching Hospital and General Hospital, Faisalabad. Electronic record from the department of medicine and their labs from the pathology department was analyzed. All cases either male or female of age above 15 years with positive reported of urine culture and sensitivity for *E.coli* MDR *E.coli* UTI cases were those who showed resistance to 2 or more of the three antimicrobial groups: (1) β -lactams (2) Quinolones (3) Aminoglycosides. Age, gender, urine WBC's, and results of urine culture and sensitivity were noted on a designed proforma.

After approval from the hospital ethical committee, electronic medical records of outdoor, indoor and emergency Department, patients from Medicine, urology, gynaecology or surgery, in Madinah Teaching Hospital, Faisalabad. Along with the demographic variables urine WBC's, and results of urine culture and sensitivity was noted. Antibiotic sensitivity pattern of all the *E.coli* resistant UTI cases was analyzed.

After the identification of the microbe, anti-microbial sensitivity was accessed using Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method on the Mueller-Hinton agar. The antimicrobial susceptibility test was performed against *E. coli* strains by using the following antibiotics: Piperacilin, Amoxicilin-Calvulanic, Pipmedic Acid, Cefipime, Ceftriaxone,

Cefuroxime, Cefoperazone sulbactam, Ceftazidime, Cephadrine, Ciprofloxacin, Ofloxacin, Levofloxacin, orfloxacin, Nitrofurantoin, Amikacin, Tombramycin, Gentamycin, Linzolid, Doxylylin, Sulphamethoxazole, Imipenem, Meropenem, Aztronam in order to obtain antibiogram.

All the variables will be analyzed using SPSS 20. All the nominal variables were expressed as percentages and the numerical data was expressed as mean with standard deviation. To control the effect modifiers, data was stratified for age and gender and post-stratification chi square will be applied to see the

effect on the outcome. P-value of ≤ 0.05 will be taken significant.

RESULTS:

In this retrospective study, 187 cases of UTI with a positive culture showing *E. coli* were identified from 2015 to 2018. Almost two third of these patients were females; 38% patients were male and 62% patients were females, with female to male ratio of about 2:1.

Mean age was 51.48 years with a standard deviation of ± 17.44 , ranging from 18 to 90 years.

Among all the cases of *E. coli* UTI, frequency of MDR was 66.8% (n=125) and rest 33.2% (n= 62) cases were not MDR UTI. (Table no. 1). Among these MDR *E.coli* UTI cases, 63.2% (n=79) were female and rest 36.8% (n=46) were males patients.

Table 1: Showing the percentage of MDR *E.coli* cases among the *E. coli* UTI cases

MDRE UTI	Cases	Percent
Yes	125/187	66.8%
No	62/187	33.2%

Among the total 187 cases, 97.3% patients were resistant to beta-lactam antibiotics, 95.7% were resistant to quinolones and 68.4% were resistant to aminoglycosides.

Effect modifiers like age and gender, were controlled through stratification and post stratification chi square test was applied. (Tables no. 2 and table no. 3)

Age of the patients was stratified into young, middle, old. Those of 18 to 35 years were grouped into young category, 36 to 60 into middle age and 61 to 90 into old age group. Post stratification chi square test was statistically significant for all categories of age but not statistically significant for gender.

Table 2: Post- stratification chi square applied for age in relation with MDR *E.coli* UTI cases

		MDR <i>E.coli</i> UTIs		Total
		Yes	No	yes
Age	Young	22	17	39
	Middle	68	29	97
	Old	35	16	51
Total		125	62	187

Chi square test = 2.45 p-value = 0.293

Table 3: Post- stratification chi square applied for gender in relation with MDR *E.coli* UTI cases

		MDR <i>E.coli</i> UTIs		Total
		Yes	No	Yes
Gender	Male	46	25	71
	Female	79	37	116
Total		125	62	187

Chi square test = 0.218 p-value = 0.640

When comparing frequencies of the MDR *E.coli* UTI cases resistant to individual groups of antibiotics, the relation was statistically significant for all the three groups individually i.e. beta-lactams, quinolones and aminoglycosides (with p value < 0.05). (Table no 4, 5 and 6)

Among the MDR *E.coli* UTI cases, 99% of the cases were resistant to one or more antimicrobials of the aminoglycoside family (which was statistically significant, $p = 0.000$). Similarly, 100% cases were resistant to one or more antimicrobials of both the beta-lactams and quinolones group (which was also

statistically significant, $p = 0.001$ and 0.000 , respectively).

Table 4: showing relation of MDR E.coli UTI cases with cases resistant to Aminoglycosides

		MDR E.coli UTIs		Total
		Yes	No	Yes
Resistant to Aminoglycosides	Yes	124	4	128
	No	1	58	59
Total		125	62	187

Chi square test = 165.08 p-value = 0.000

Table 5: showing relation of MDR E.coli UTI cases with cases resistant to beta-lactams

		MDRE UTIs		Total
		Yes	No	Yes
Resistant to Beta-lactams	Yes	125	57	182
	No	0	5	5
Total		125	62	187

Chi square test = 10.358 p-value = 0.001

Table 6: showing relation of MDR E.coli UTI cases with cases resistant to quinolones

		MDRE UTIs		Total
		Yes	no	yes
Resistant to Quinolones	yes	125	54	179
	no	0	8	8
Total		125	62	187

Chi square test = 16.850 p-value = 0.000

DISCUSSION:

Urinary tract infections are commonly seen in all age groups and in both genders. Children and old age group people are more affected and female gender is a significant risk factor. It is also one of the most common hospital acquired infections patients can get when admitted in the wards with other diagnosis. As antimicrobial resistance of E. coli is rising, it becomes very difficult for the consultants to select an appropriate oral anti-microbial.

Phase I of this study was published showing the demographic variables and prevalence of MDR E. coli UTI cases of Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan. This is the second phase of this study in which

antimicrobial sensitivity pattern was analyzed. To our knowledge, the prevalence of UTI near Multan has been first time documented in this study with respect to different uropathogens and risk factors including age and gender groups and demographic and gender-wise distribution of UTI patients. The patients included in the study belong to different areas near Multan where socioeconomic status of the patients is a problem of growing concern. Data was collected on the basis of their location and socioeconomic status that may contribute in the development of UTI. Mostly UTI-associated patients belong to less developing areas that have no access to pure water, poor sanitary condition, poor personal hygiene, and low literacy rate in population. Our results showed

that UTI was more prevalent in rural areas and less prevalent in urban areas. Most of the UTI cases belong to urban area similar to the study by Dhodi et al. [32]. The prevalence of UTI was varying according to geographical and regional locations.

A study conducted in Nepal, South Asia urine samples for culture and sensitivity and reported that microbes growth was seen in around 25.5% samples showed. More than 60% of these cases showing bacteriuria were females; and among these culture positive cases, six different microbes were observed, *E. coli* in more than half of these cases (53%) followed by *K. pneumoniae* (21.43%), *Pseudomonas* (12.3%), *Proteus* (7.1%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (4%) and *Proteus mirabilis* (2%). These gram -ive microbes were sensitive to gentamicin (57%) and ceftriaxone (51%); nitrofurantoin also showed significant sensitivity (45.75%), and least sensitivity was observed with ampicillin (5.32%). [7]

McAllister R, et al. reported that in the patients with diagnosed with MDR UTI, asymptomatic pyuria was seen in 15% cases in patients more than 80 years of age. They reported that UTIs are more among patients of advanced age group, those with genital or urinary tract anatomical anomalies, those with history of renal stones, bladder stones, recurrent episodes of dehydration, and are diabetic. [8]

In a local study done in a tertiary hospital in Multan, 150 samples with *E. coli* MRD UTI, and antimicrobial susceptibility were tested. Demographic analysis showed that patients of rural background were more affected, with female predominantly involved. Resistance was seen against imipenem, Cipro, Augmenten, as 80%, 72%, and 68%, respectively. Resistance against imipenem to that much extent is alarming. Significant results showed that TZP, AK, and F were found sensitive in vitro against *E. coli*. The situation has not been addressed seriously. [9]

A met analysis of around 25 studies with MDR UTI patients showed that major factor leading to MDR UTI was the miss use of antibiotics. This reported in 16 out of 20 studies. Other significant factors were catheterization and history of hospital stay. [10]

Another study reported after analyzing cases of UTI caused by *E. coli* and concluded that females were mostly involved and resistance was most commonly seen against trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, ampicillin, and ampicillin-sulbactam. Resistance against other antibiotics was cipro (47.3%), levo (43.6%) and cephalosporins (27.6%). MDR UTI *E.*

coli cases were around 63%; most of cases with resistance to fluoroquinolone (FQ) were MDR cases and were male. Those with history of hospital stay were resistant to 3rd gen cephalosporin and nitrofurantoin. [11]

Linsenmeyer K, et al. evaluated the data of 126 cases of Gram-ive MDR UTI. Mean age was 72.8 years and 90% were males. [12] In a study, more than 200 cases were studied to identify MDR *E. coli* UTI cases, the frequency was 54.5% (121/222). [13]

Ukah UV, et al studied reports of urine cultures which showed 1238 cases of *E. coli* UTI. Among the women 41% showed resistance to one group of anti microbial and 25% were MDR *E. coli* UTI. Outcome was not affected by factors like age, education, economic status between susceptible UTI female cases and MDR cases; but outcome was significantly affected with the history of frequent use of anti biotics for the last six months. [14]

Elsayed TI, et al. collected data of resistant cases of UTIs with history of recurrent episode, and tested them for antibiotic resistance. They reported that resistance was seen against Ampicillin in 95% cases of MDR UTI, Sulphamethoxazole/Trimethoprim 69%, Nalidixic acid 70%, Norfloxacin 59%, Gentamicin 31%, Nitrofurantoin 16%, Cephalothin 93% and Imipenem 2%. The overall incidence of MDR *e. coli* UTI cases came to be 95% among the total MDR UTI cases. They also reported that the multi- drug resistance was more in ESBL producers as compared to non-ESBL producers. Gentamicin and imipenem had no significant relation with ESBL. [15]

A study carried out in Chicago included 676 cases diagnosed on urine culture reporting; one third of these were having no symptoms. Among the total cases 12.3% cases were due to non-Enterobacteriaceae. Mean age was 44 years, around 80% were females. With previous use of antimicrobial (in 3 months), seen in 27% cases, it became to major risk factor. Only 12% cases were resistant to FQs. [16]

A large study done in Europe included around 30 countries and collected data regarding multi-drug-resistant cases of infections involving the urinary tract. *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* infections were the most prevalent pathogens in MDR cases in most of the countries. Resistance was seen to penicillins (65%), aminoglycosides (19%) and FQs (44%) among all the *E. coli* cases. With every crossing year, the number of cases of ESBL-positive *E. coli* infections also increased all around in the EU. [17]

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